

THE ROLE OF VITAMINS AND CALCIUM IN THE DIET IN THE UTILISATION OF PROTEINS.

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Absence of vitamin A, B₁, B₂, B-complex or D from the diet has very little effect on the digestibility of casein but increases the biological value. The term B₂ includes all the heat-stable factors of vitamin B complex. Autoclaving decreases the biological value while absence of calcium has no effect.

The determination of the percentage of a digested protein that is retained by an animal or, in other words, of its biological value is always carried out with diets containing adequate amounts of the necessary vitamins and of minerals. In the estimation of the relative nutritive values of proteins from different sources, protein is the only variable factor in the diets. No systematic experiments appear to have been undertaken to find out the role of the different vitamins and minerals in the utilisation of proteins by animals. Some experiments have been carried out to find out the relation between the proportion of proteins in the diet and vitamin B requirement. Thus Funk *et al.* (*Compt. rend. Soc. Biol.*, 1925, 92, 997) experimenting with pigeons found that as the proportion of protein in diet increased the vitamin B requirement decreased. On the other hand, Hartwell (*Biochem. J.*, 1925, 19, 1074) and also Nelson (*J. Home Economics*, 1926, 18, 383) report that high protein diet increases the need for liberal intake of vitamin B. Finally, Sherman and Gloy (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1937, 74, 117) experimenting with rats and with casein as the protein in diets found that varying the percentage of protein in the diet between 12 and 54 had no effect on the period of survival of the rats in the absence of vitamin B. They concluded that in the estimation of vitamin B, basal diets might vary widely in protein content and still yield interchangeable results.

The aim of the present investigation, which was carried out with rats as experimental animals, was to find out the effect of the absence of vitamins A, D, B₁, B₂ and B complex and of calcium on the biological value of a protein (casein) by the balance sheet method. With rats as experimental animals the effect of vitamin C could not be investigated. Except in the determination of the effect of calcium the casein was freed from all vitamins by autoclaving it under pressure and the effect of this treatment on the biological value of casein was first determined. The experiments were all carried out with diets containing 10% protein.

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

The technique of the experiment was the same as that employed in the previous communications from this laboratory (*Ind. J. Med. Res.*, 1938, 26, 177; 1936, 23, 789; 1937, 24, 1001, 1043; *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 16, 189, 209). In determining the role of vitamins, the casein was freed from vitamins by heating it in an autoclave and the diets contained adequate and constant amounts of salt mixture. The butter-fat was replaced by vitamin-free vegetable fat.

(i) *Effect of Autoclaving.*—All the vitamins and minerals were supplied in equal amounts in both the series. The results are given in Table II.

(ii) *Effect of Vitamin B Complex.*—Equal amounts of vitamins A and D were supplied in the form of cod-liver oil in both the series. Vitamin B complex was supplied in one series in the form of marmite and withheld from the other. The results are indicated in Table III.

(iii) *Effect of Vitamin B₁.*—Vitamins A and D (cod-liver oil) were supplied in both the series. Vitamin B₁ was withheld from one series by previously heating the marmite supplied in an autoclave. The results are indicated in Table IV.

(iv) *Effect of Vitamin B₂.*—Cod-liver oil was supplied in both the series. In one series international vitamin B₁ preparation and autoclaved marmite were daily supplied while autoclaved marmite was not supplied in the other series. Results are to be found in Table V. The term B₂ thus includes all the heat-stable factors of vitamin B complex.

(v) *Effect of Vitamin A.*—Vitamin A was supplied as β -carotene and vitamin D in the form of the international preparation of irradiated ergosterol in one series while β -carotene was withheld from the other. Marmite was given in both the series. Data are given in Table VI.

(vi) *Effect of Vitamin D.*—The experiments were similar to the above except that the international vitamin D preparation was withheld from one series. Results are indicated in Table VII.

(vii) *Effect of Calcium.*—The experiments were performed with unheated calcium-free casein and the vitamins were supplied in both the series. Calcium of the salt mixture as well as calcium carbonate were omitted from one series of rats which did not receive any calcium in their diets. Results are indicated in Table VIII.

Table I represents the nitrogen eliminations with protein-free diets.

TABLE I.

With nitrogen-free ration.

(Figures of intake and excretion represent daily averages).

Rat No.	Average wt.	Food intake.	Urinary N.	Faecal nitrogen	
				Total.	Per g of food intake.
501	225 g.	9.1 g.	54.7 mg.	14.34 mg.	1.57 mg.
502	208	8.0	55.95	13.44	1.67
503	210.5	7.1	55.95	11.6	1.63
504	221	9.1	54.07	13.6	1.5
505	222.5	6.5	57.2	14.26	2.19
506	232	9.2	49.9	19.6	2.13
507	224.5	9.9	58.9	11.9	1.2
508	227	9.9	46.1	13.38	1.35
509	219	10	49.6	24.2	2.42
510	222.5	9.25	48.9	21.5	2.32
511	235.5	8.4	45.3	15.1	1.80
512	234	7.8	42.05	12.88	1.65
513	243.5	10	33.6	22.8	2.28
514	241.5	7.5	50.8	15.74	2.1
515	226.5	10	45.6	26.3	2.63
516	236	10	61.9	24.7	2.47
517	214	8.4	44.2	17.2	2.48
518	216.5	7.7	39.0	10.9	1.42

TABLE II.
Effect of autoclaving on the B.V. of casein.

(Figures of intake and excretion represent daily averages).

Rat No.	Av. body wt.	Diet	Intake		Faecal nitrogen		Food absorbed		Urinary nitrogen		Food utilisation	*B.V.	*D	
			Food.	Nitrogen.	Total.	Endo.	Exo.	Total.	Endo.	Exo.				
513	233.5 g.	unheated casein diet.	12.0 g.	191.2 mg.	35.48 mg.	27.36 mg.	8.12 mg.	183.1 mg.	86.8 mg.	33.6 mg.	53.2 mg.	129.9 mg.	70.92	95.8
514	233		10.42	166.0	32.49	21.89	10.60	155.4	100.8	50.8	50.0	105.4	67.83	93.64
515	214		9.5	151.3	34.83	24.99	9.84	141.5	91.18	45.6	45.58	96.92	68.50	93.51
516	226.5	10% autoclaved casein diet.	12.56	198.0	36.28	31.01	15.27	182.7	143.8	61.9	81.9	100.8	55.21	92.25
517	201		10.8	170.3	38.60	26.79	11.81	158.5	118.2	44.2	74.0	84.5	53.30	93.1
518	205		11.42	180.1	31.60	16.22	15.38	164.7	108.2	39.0	69.2	95.5	57.94	91.5

* In Table II—VIII, B.V. denotes Biological and D, the digestibility values.

TABLE III.

Effect of withholding vitamin B complex (marmite) from the diet.

(Figures of intake and excretion represent daily averages).

Rat No.	Av. body wt.	Diet.	Intake		Faecal nitrogen		Food absorbed.		Urinary nitrogen		N utilised	B. V.	D.	
			Food.	Nitrogen.	Total.	Endo.	Exo	Total.	Endo.	Exo.				
511	234 g.	Complete	14.4	196.6 mg.	45.24 mg.	25.92 mg.	19.32 mg.	117.28 mg.	126.73 mg.	45.3 mg.	81.43 mg.	95.85 mg.	54.06	90.17
512	231.5		12.0	163.8	32.73	19.80	12.93	150.87	106.30	42.05	64.25	86.62	57.41	92.11
513	241	Without marmite.	10.6	144.7	39.37	24.17	15.20	129.50	72.27	33.6	38.67	90.83	70.14	89.5
514	241		13.2	180.2	39.58	27.72	11.86	168.34	96.36	50.8	45.56	122.78	72.94	93.42
515	223.5		13.6	185.6	53.54	35.77	17.77	167.83	88.79	45.6	43.19	124.64	74.27	90.43
516	232		14.1	192.5	50.17	34.83	15.34	177.16	116.22	61.9	54.32	122.84	69.34	92.03

TABLE IV.

Effect of omitting vitamin B₁ from the diet.

(Figures of intake and excretion represent daily averages).

Rat No.	Av. wt. body	Diet.	Intake		Faecal nitrogen		Food absorbed		Urinary nitrogen		Food utilised	B. V.	D.	
			Food.	Nitrogen.	Total.	Endo.	Exo.	Total.	Endo.	Exo.				
507	210 g.	Complete	10.63	168.4	22.59	12.76	9.83	158.6	130.2	58.9	71.3	87.3	55.05	94.20
508	218		12.4	196.4	25.25	16.74	8.51	187.9	128.4	46.1	82.3	105.6	50.31	95.65
509	205	Without B ₁	10.2	161.5	35.27	24.68	10.59	150.9	104.8	49.6	55.2	95.7	63.40	93.41
510	204.5		9.46	149.8	33.35	21.95	11.40	138.4	102.7	48.9	53.8	84.6	61.14	92.33
517	198		9.96	157.8	37.99	24.71	13.28	144.5	101.1	44.2	56.9	87.6	60.62	91.60
518	202		9.25	146.5	24.74	13.13	11.61	134.9	91.1	39.0	52.1	82.8	61.43	92.02

TABLE V.

Effect of omitting vitamin B₂ from the diet.

(Figures of intake and excretion represent daily averages).

Rat No	Av. body wt.	Diet	Intake		Urinary nitrogen		Food absorbed		Urinary nitrogen		Food utilised.	B.V	D.	
			Food.	Nitrogen.	Total.	Endo.	Exo.	Total.	Endo.	Exo.				
511	220 g	Complete diet.	13.4 g.	219.8 mg.	34.85 mg.	24.12 mg.	10.73 mg.	209.1 mg.	140.4 mg.	45.3 mg.	95.1 mg.	114.0 mg.	54.5	95.20
512	217.5		10.65	174.6	28.57	17.57	11.00	163.6	111.0	42.05	68.95	94.65	57.85	93.71
513	230		12.40	203.3	42.04	28.26	13.78	189.5	97.8	33.6	64.2	125.3	66.1	93.24
514	229	Without vit. B ₂	9.94	163.0	34.78	20.87	13.91	149.1	99.7	50.8	48.9	100.2	67.21	91.51
515	210.5		11.32	185.7	38.01	29.78	8.23	177.5	109.4	45.6	63.8	113.7	64.03	95.62
516	223		15.20	216.5	44.97	32.60	12.37	204.1	135.1	61.9	73.2	130.9	64.11	94.30

TABLE VI.
Effect of omitting vitamin A from the diet.

(Figures of intake and excretion represent daily averages).

Rat No	Av. body wt.	Diet.	Intake		Faecal nitrogen		Absorbed N ₂		Urinary nitrogen		Food N ₂ excreted	B. V. D.
			Food. Nitrogen.	Total.	Endo.	Exo.	Total.	Endo.	Exo.			
505	237 g.	Complete	142.6 mg.	31.56 mg.	21.75 mg.	9.81 mg.	132.79 mg.	113.82 mg.	57.2 mg.	56.62 mg.	76.17 mg.	93.12
506	248.5	Complete	135.4	28.20	20.09	8.11	127.29	107.03	49.9	57.13	70.16	94.01
507	239	Vitamin A.	142.05	19.98	11.88	8.10	133.95	101.21	58.9	42.31	91.64	68.40
508	245.5	Vitamin A.	135.4	20.13	12.73	7.40	128.00	85.13	46.1	39.03	88.97	69.50
509	232.5	Without vitamin A.	142.2	30.67	23.98	6.69	135.51	93.52	49.6	43.92	91.59	67.59
510	240	Without vitamin A.	142.4	35.06	23.01	12.05	130.35	91.22	48.9	42.32	88.03	67.53

TABLE VII.
Effect of omitting vitamin D from the diet.
 (Figures of intake and excretion represent daily averages).

Rat No.	Av. body wt.	Diet.	Intake		Faecal nitrogen		Absorption		Urinary nitrogen		Zinc	B.V. D.		
			Food.	Nitrogen.	Total.	Endo.	Exo.	Total.	Endo.	Exo.			Total.	Endo.
501	216 g.	Complete diet.	6.7 g.	85.9 mg.	15.55 mg.	10.52 mg.	5.03 mg.	80.97 mg.	90.58 mg.	54.7 mg.	35.88 mg.	45.09 mg.	55.6	94.15
502	195		9.0	115.7	23.68	15.03	8.65	107.05	102.55	55.95	46.60	60.45	56.47	92.52
503	197	Without vitamin D	7.2	92.6	18.99	11.74	7.25	85.35	86.67	55.95	30.72	54.63	64.01	92.17
504	210		9.04	116.2	23.32	13.56	9.76	106.44	93.31	54.07	39.24	67.20	63.13	91.60
511	223.5		7.99	102.8	21.28	14.38	6.90	95.9	78.61	45.30	33.31	62.59	65.27	93.28
512	221.5		8.35	107.4	19.61	13.78	5.83	101.57	78.91	42.05	36.86	64.71	63.71	94.66

TABLE VIII.

Effect of omitting calcium from the diet.

(Figures of intake and excretion represent daily averages).

Rat No.	Av body wt.	Diet.	Intake		Faecal nitrogen		Zn absorbed	Urinary nitrogen		Zn deposited	B. V. D.			
			Food.	Nitrogen.	Total.	Endo.		Exo.	Total.			Endo.	Exo.	
501	211 g.	Complete diet.	13.9 g.	221.2 mg.	36.14 mg.	21.82 mg.	14.32 mg.	206.88 mg.	114.65 mg.	54.70 mg.	59.95 mg.	146.93 mg.	71.02	93.52
502	193		14.0	222.7	38.39	23.38	15.01	207.69	118.05	55.95	62.10	145.59	70.10	93.3
503	192.5	Without calcium.	13.9	221.2	24.87	22.66	2.21	218.99	120.50	55.95	64.55	154.44	70.57	99.00
504	205		13.9	221.2	22.80	20.85	1.95	219.25	119.19	54.07	65.12	154.13	70.30	99.12
505	207.5		13.7	218.5	32.30	30.0	2.30	216.20	121.18	57.20	63.98	152.22	70.40	98.95
506	215		13.3	210.9	30.32	28.33	1.99	208.91	112.32	49.90	62.42	146.49	70.12	99.50

DISCUSSION.

The observed biological value (70.0) of unheated casein at 10% level agrees with the value obtained by previous workers like Mitchell, Boas Fixsen and also by Kik (*Proc. Soc. Exp. Biol. Med.*, 1937, 37, 129).

Effect of Heat Treatment.—There is some controversy regarding the effect of heat treatment on the biological value and digestibility of proteins. Seegers and Schultz (*J. Nutrition*, 1936, 11, 5, Proc.) observed that autoclaving of beef muscle for 1 hour at 15 lbs. pressure and of casein for 2 hours at 120° or at 150° for 30 minutes had no effect on the biological value of the proteins. Very recently Morgan and Loveen (*J. Nutrition*, 1938, 16, 115) have observed that heating for 30 minutes at 140° reduced the biological value of casein as tested on rats from 69 to 57—a loss of 17%—and lowered the digestibility by 4%. In this investigation autoclaving the casein at 120° for 2 hours lowered the biological value by about 20% and the digestibility by about 2%. In a previous investigation from this laboratory Basu, Nath and Mukherjee (*Indian J. Med. Res.*, 1937, 24, 1001) found that heating the soyabean lowered the biological value of its proteins.

Effect of the Absence of the Vitamins.—It is remarkable that omitting the vitamins from the diet always increased the biological value of casein in the short term experiments. Of course, if the experiments in the absence of vitamins are prolonged for a long time, the rats would lose appetite, take insufficient food and get emaciated. In these short period experiments the rats were not completely depleted of their body store of the particular vitamin although the latter was omitted from the diets. The reason why the absence of a particular vitamin from the diet caused a better retention of the protein was probably that in the absence of the vitamin the metabolism and oxidation of the amino-acids of the protein were depressed which caused a diminished elimination of nitrogen in the urine and hence a higher retention of the nitrogen.

Effect of Calcium.—Recently Ranganathan and Rau (*Nature*, 1938, 142, 165) reported that the addition of calcium to the Madras diet considerably increased the biological value and digestibility of the proteins of the diet as measured by rat experiments. In the present investigation, which was conducted with calcium-free casein, experiments conducted in the presence of and in the complete absence of calcium from the salt mixture in the diet, gave identical values for the biological value of casein. It appears that calcium has no effect on the biological value of protein.